

PAREMIOLOGY AS A STUDY OBJECT OF PHRASEOLOGY

Ruzikulov Elyor Shukurovich

Samarkand State University of Architecture and Construction

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Abstract. *In this article, the main attention was paid to the semantic interpretation of paremiology, which is part of phraseology along with phraseological units. Also, semantic and linguistic aspects of paremiological units in English and Uzbek languages were analyzed and semantic groups of English proverbs were studied. Similar and different aspects of English and Uzbek proverbs from the linguistic and cultural point of view were studied, and for the first time paremiological units related to the themes of hospitality, neighborliness, kinship and kinship in English and Uzbek languages were compared linguistically and culturally. analysis and revealing some characteristics of communicative phraseological units, comparative analysis of the semantics of communicative phraseological units from a linguistic and cultural point of view within the framework of English and Uzbek languages.*

Keywords: *paremiology, semantics, phraseology, linguistic culture, lexicon, phraseological combinations, language units, words and stable combinations, archaic elements, variants, nominative function, etc.*

Many things are being done in our country in order to take a worthy place in the world community. In recent years, great attention has been paid to science, education and learning foreign languages. After all, attention paid to education means attention paid to the future. As a clear proof of the idea, our president SH.M. We can cite the following comments of Mirziyoyev: "We have raised investment in human capital to the level of state policy, deeply realizing that the key to modern development lies in science and education." [1]. In particular, great attention was paid to teaching and learning foreign languages in our country. This, in turn, is the reason for the opening of many researches and news related to the field of the English language.

It is known that language is the main means of communication between people. Phraseological units of one or another language play an important role in the transmission of the national and cultural lifestyle, customs and traditions, folklore, art and science of a certain people from generation to generation. In the communication of each language, these units have their important place, and a certain language cannot be imagined without the phraseological layer of that language.

Today, in modern linguistics, like many other fields, the department of phraseology is widely studied.

As we all know, language is the most important means of communication between people, the main tool of exchange of ideas, which ensures the development of society's thinking, which transmits cultural-spiritual and historical traditions from generation to generation. Language is also a treasure of national culture. The economic and social system, art, culture, artistic literature, tradition, folk oral creativity of the place where each nation lives and its transmission from generation to generation is the national-cultural semantics of the language [2:7-286].

Semantics is present in all layers of language: grammar, lexis, phonetics. But the national cultural semantics is clearly manifested in the units of the language in action. Such language units are words and stable compounds. In the process of speaking, we use our thoughts not only with

the help of words, but also with the units formed by the stable connection of two or more words, which enter the speech ready. These units not only describe our speech, but also describe it in a meaningful, concise, colorful way.

In linguistics, such units are studied by the Department of Phraseology. Phraseology (from the Greek "phrasis" - expression, expression and logic) is such a branch of linguistics that differs from other branches in its ready-made entry into speech, lexical and semantic incompatibility, and semantic stability. . The main focus of phraseology as a separate branch of linguistics is to study the nature of phraseologisms and their categorical features, as well as to determine the guidelines for the use of phraseologisms in speech. Its main important problem is to differentiate and distinguish phraseologisms from word combinations formed in speech and to identify phraseologisms accordingly.

Phraseology can be cited as a treasure of a certain language.

Because phraseology shows the history, culture and uniqueness of the people. Phraseologisms mainly reflect the customs and traditions of the nation. But in the phraseology of the English language, along with phraseological combinations that express national traditions, there are also international phraseology. Archaic elements have been preserved in some phraseological combinations.

It is wrong to look at phraseological units only as a means of decorating speech, they are units that have a highly informative nature and perform a nominative and communicative function in the language, like other language units. There is not a single language without phraseological units [3:P. 21].

The research conducted by English and American linguists makes up a relatively small percentage of English phraseology, and theoretical problems such as the main phraseological problems and the interrelationship of words, the variation of phraseological units, the methods of studying phraseology, the development of phraseology as a science are mainly Russian linguists, A.V. Kunin, V.V. Vinogradov, H.M. Shansky, T.N. Developed by the Fedulenkovas. [4: C. 34.].

Phraseology is considered one of the complex branches of linguistics, and it is directly related to a number of departments of linguistics, including lexicology, stylistics, semantics, etymology, morphology, and grammar. In the study of phraseology, in addition to the fields listed above, it is necessary to be aware of such subjects as country studies, phonetics, philosophy, history of sciences, and logic.

It is known that any phraseological units are made up of words. The word is the research object of lexicology. The fact that lexicology and phraseology are interrelated fields is shown in the fact that in the analysis of words that are components of phraseological combinations, information about lexicology is necessarily referred to. Also, the study of phraseology as a component of lexicology for many years proves that these two fields are directly related to each other.

The features of lexical meaning studied in semantics serve to express the semantic peculiarities of phraseological units and to distinguish different types of meaning in the phraseological field.

A word in a phraseological combination does not always lose its morphological features, morphology allows to study preserved and lost features.

Phraseology includes compounds with different structures, i.e. phrases and sentences. Syntax information is used in the grammatical and functional analysis of the above units.

The stylistic possibility of phraseology is very important. Phraseological stylistics researches the stylistic features of phraseological units and relies on the experience of lexical stylistics in this field, the analysis of various stylistic units. Because phraseological units, in addition to performing a nominative function in the language, are distinguished by having a certain emotionality and expressive properties.

The origin and history of the language is a necessary part of the etymological analysis of phraseological units.

In English, as well as in other languages, it is important and interesting to study the national-cultural semantics of the language. Because they can embody the unique internal structures of the language, natural peculiarities, economic and social structure of the country, art, customs and history from generation to generation. They have information about children's national games, currency, national medicine, hunting and fishing, flora and fauna, human appearance, clothing and lifestyle, and many other features of the national mentality. topics will be reflected [5:P.163].

National-cultural semantics is reflected in all departments of linguistics, morphology, syntax, and even phonetics. Only it can be more vividly expressed in phraseological units that can directly reflect the culture of the nation, and are integrated and often used in colloquial speech.

If we look at the history of the emergence of phraseology, it does not have a very long history, like a number of other departments of linguistics.

Until phraseology was formed as a separate discipline, it was considered a part of lexicology. Although Russian linguists were first interested in the problems of phraseology, it was first introduced as a separate term by Western linguist Sh. Used by Bally. In his works "Essays on Stylistics" and "Stylistics of the French Language", he looked at word combinations as a whole system, which can be used as a whole, arising from the uniqueness of their grammatical and lexical features, syntactic structure and meaning. tried to prove unity. In the first work, Charles Bally distinguished four types of word combinations: free compounds compounds used in their own sense regular compounds relatively freely connected compounds (some changes can be made) phraseological lines (in which two or more units combine to express a single meaning, but changes can be made to its order); phraseological units (which have completely lost their meaning, includes units whose order of components is fixed. [6: C.32].

In his next work "French Stylistics" he interpreted the usual combinations and phraseological lines as a component of free combinations and phraseological units. Although these views of his have caused many debates, they have stimulated the development of phraseology as a separate science.

Russian linguist Polivanov was the first to analyze as a separate branch of linguistics, and he justified that phraseology is not a component of lexicology or stylistics, but an independent branch of linguistics: "Lexicology is the lexical meaning of words, morphology is the grammatical meaning of words. nouns, and syntax studies the grammatical meanings of word combinations. But there is a need for a department of linguistics that studies the individual meanings of isolated, figurative word combinations." He is one of the linguists who emphasized that phraseology is an important department in linguistics, like morphology or phonetics [7:C.201-202].

After B.A. Polivanov, Larin is one of the linguists who proposed studying phraseology as a separate branch of linguistics. "Phraseology as a branch of linguistics is still in the "hidden stage of development", it has not yet fully developed as a separate science. However, its formation as a

separate science requires great necessity in today's linguistics. Because it is not a secret to anyone that problems related to this field are sometimes solved by lexicography, and sometimes by stylistics or synthesis" [8: P.61].

Phraseology as a separate branch of linguistics was developed by the great Russian linguist V.V. Vinogradov also considered it. He semantically classifies phraseological units in the Russian language, and this, in turn, was one of the great steps of his work on phraseology for that time. But even later, his work was not recognized as a separate branch of phraseology. Because Vinogradov analyzed phraseology in a broad way, the difference between phraseological units and simple word combinations was not defined in his works on phraseology. Vinogradov did not propose a separate definition of phraseological units in the language, taking into account that phraseological units are too close to words, he included his theory in the framework of the grammatical analysis of the word [9: P.6]. Later, it was separated from lexicology as a separate branch of linguistics in the second half of the 20th century.

A number of Uzbek scientists, including Shavkat Rahmatullayev, played a significant role in the development of phraseology, and in turn, in the emergence of phraseology in Uzbek linguistics. A number of his scientific studies devoted to the field of phraseology made a great contribution to the development of the phraseology of the Uzbek language. His "Main Meaning Types of Phraseological Combinations", "Explanatory Phraseological Dictionary of the Uzbek Language", "Short Phraseological Dictionary of the Uzbek Language", "Main Meaning Types of Phraseological Combinations", "Osnovnie grammatichicheskie osobennosti obraznix" He contributed to the phraseology of the Uzbek language with a number of scientific works such as "glagolnix frazeologicheskikh yedinetsovremennogo uzbekskogo yazika".

Including Y. Pinkhasov, he achieved great success in studying phraseological units. He contributed with his works "Current Uzbek Literary Language", "About the Phraseology of the Uzbek Language". B. Yoldoshev, Abdugofur and Abdumurad Mamatov also played a significant role in the development of Uzbek phraseology.

The stylistic possibility of phraseology is very important. Phraseological stylistics studies the stylistic features of phraseological combinations and relies on the experience of lexical stylistics and the analysis of various stylistic units in this field. After all, phraseological combinations are distinguished by having a certain emotionality and expressive properties, in addition to performing a nominative function in the language.

In short, the field of phraseology in linguistics is considered one of the fields that does not have a long history. It was studied as part of lexicology for many years until it was separated as a separate department. Despite the fact that a lot of research has been done in the field of phraseology, it still has many aspects that have not yet been discovered.

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